

BIO-INSPIRED NEUROMORPHIC NETWORK BASED ON CARBON NANOTUBE/POLYMER COMPOSITES

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Control and health management of automatic systems, such as UAV, is inevitably subject to unexpected exogenous threats from failures, environmental changes, battle damage, and external disturbances, etc. Current automatic control and health management systems for the aerial vehicles rely on Si circuits programmed by human. However, the Si circuits are vulnerable when they experience unanticipated threats without preprogrammed solutions, and consume significant energy. The human brain, on the other hand, is composed of neuronal networks connected by $\sim 10^{15}$ synapses. The realization of a physical device with the functions of a biological synapse is essential to emulate the neuronal networks. Electronic devices such as floating gate silicon transistors, nanoparticle organic transistors, resistive switches, memristors, phase change memory, and carbon nanotube (CNT) transistors could hardly generate dynamic logic functions of the biological synapse. Although the synaptic dynamic function could be emulated by integrating the electric devices with peripheral circuits, modifying the testing conditions, and large scale Si neuromorphic circuits, the circuits consumed substantially more energy than a biological synapse, which make it hard to scale up the circuits to a size comparable with the brain.

In this work, we report an electronic device, synapstor, based on CNT/polymer composite that can emulate the elementary dynamic logic, memory, and learning functions of the biological synapse. The synapstor can process spatiotemporally correlated spikes, facilitate memory with long-term potentiation (LTP) or depression (LTD), and learn with spike-timing dependent plasticity (STDP). CNT has been considered as an alternative material to replace silicon in future electronic circuits due to its nanoscale size and unique electronic properties [1]. We designed and fabricated the synapstor with a transistor-like structure in order to operate it with extremely low energy consumption (Figure 1a). A

randomly aligned CNT network was coated onto the surface of a silicon dioxide layer on a silicon chip. The synapstor channel was made from a strip of randomly distributed single-walled CNT network. A Ti/Au layer was deposited onto the CNT network to form the source and drain electrodes. A layer of poly(ethylene glycol) monomethyl ether (PEG) was spin-coated and cross-linked on the top of the CNT network using e-beam lithography, and a Ti/Al layer were deposited onto the top of the PEG layer as a gate electrode. An electrochemical cell was then integrated in the transistor gate by sandwiching the hydrogen doped PEG electrolyte between the CNT channel and the Ti/Al gate electrode.

To test the synapstor under the condition similar to a biological synapse (Figure 1b), a customized electronic circuit was used to generate and apply pre- and post-synaptic spikes on the gate and drain electrodes of the synapstor, and a customized current-to-voltage converter was used to detect the post-synaptic current with low noise. Pre- and post-synaptic spikes were applied on the gate and drain electrodes, respectively, of the synapstor, and post-synaptic currents were measured through the drain of the synapstor. The post-synaptic currents were amplified and converted to analog voltage signals. The synaptic strength was measured from the amplitude of an excitatory post-synaptic current (EPSC) triggered by a pre-synaptic spike with an amplitude of 5 V and 1 ms duration (Figure 1c). Typical temporal responses of the CNT synapse to a 5 V pre-synaptic spike with 1 ms duration are shown in Figure 1d. The pre-synaptic spike triggers EPSC above the resting current, which reaches a peak value at the end of the spike, and gradually decays back to the resting current in ~ 23.7 ms, which is similar to EPSC in a biological excitatory synapse. The EPSC amplitude increased with the increasing amplitude and duration of the pre-synaptic spikes. When the PEG polymer with the mobile hydrogen ions in the CNT synapse was replaced by an epoxy

polymer layer without any mobile ions in a control device, no EPSC was observed. EPSC could be triggered when the pre-synaptic spike drives the hydrogen ions inside the PEG polymer towards the CNT channel, which attracts and accumulates the electrons in the CNTs and induces the post-synaptic current through the CNT channel (Figure 1d). After the spike ends, the hydrogen ions gradually drift back to their equilibrium positions in the polymer, inducing EPSC. The randomly connected CNT network may contribute to the large statistic variation of EPSC. The average energy consumption for the CNT synapse to trigger an EPSC is 7.5 pJ/spike, which is significantly lower than the energy consumption by conventional CMOS circuit (900 pJ/spike).

Long-term synaptic plasticity has been realized as the underlying mechanism for learning and memory in the brain. The long-term plasticity behavior of the synapstor was demonstrated by modifying the synaptic strength with pre- and post-synaptic spikes. As shown in Figure 1e, after applying two hundred post-synaptic spikes, the EPSC amplitude is increased, resulting in long-term potentiation (LTP) in the synapstor; whereas after applying one hundred pre-synaptic spikes, the EPSC amplitude is decreased, inducing the long-term depression (LTD). The synaptic strength in a synapstor can be continuously and reversibly modified to desired analog values by applying a series of pre- and post-synaptic spikes with different amplitudes. The rate of change in the synaptic strength increases with the increasing amplitudes of spikes.

A Synapstor-Integrated Neuromorphic Circuit (SINC) have been fabricated to emulate a biological neuron network with spatiotemporal logic, memory, massively parallel high-speed signal processing, and real-time learning functions [2]. The intelligent learning function of the SINC under the unexpected exogenous environmental changes has been demonstrated in the control of a UAV Drone.

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Figure 1. (a) A schematic diagram showing the structure of a synapstor. The inset is an AFM image of a random CNT network. (b) A scheme showing a biological synapse between a pre-synaptic neuron and a post-synaptic neuron. (c) A symbol represents the synapstor and a scheme showing that a pre-synaptic potential spike applied on its top gate triggers an excitatory post-synaptic current (EPSC) on its drain. (d) A pre-synaptic spike (top) applied on a synapstor and EPSC (bottom) triggered by the spikes are shown versus time. (e) The EPSC amplitudes in a synapstor are plotted as a function of time when the LTP (red) and the LTD (blue) stimulations are applied respectively at $t = 0$ s (marked by the arrow).

References

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